

THE STUDY OF HYPERBOLE IN THE UZBEK LINGUISTICS

Parmonov Islomjon Odiljon o'g'li

The 2nd -year student of Master's degree in

Linguistics (English), NUUz,

islomparmonov@gmail.com

ABSTRACT :With the help of certain examples, the article recognizes several distinctions and similarities between the English and Uzbek languages in terms of hyperbole. However, hyperbole is considered a conversational production process, requiring the listener to be aware of the background process. Some contrasts and similarities can be seen by comparing and analyzing exaggeration in non-genetically related languages. This study's focus is on the history of hyperbole, the scientists who developed it, their theories, various kinds of hyperbole, and its application in both spoken language and literal texts.

Key words: hyperbole, literal text, figurative meaning, stylistic trop, linguistics, linguo-pragmatics, parts of speech, sarcasm

Introduction:It is known that people from all over the world want to begin chats with the help of figurative languages, rather than saying something more merely and directly [1]. Hyperbole is a kind of figurative language where the speaker says something while meaning another thing [2]. In other words, the literal meaning of what is said does not match the intended meaning [3]. In general, hyperbole is utilized on a daily basis, making utterances more sensitive. Understanding hyperbole, on the other hand, sometimes necessitates listeners being more attentive and conscious of the back process. Analyzing exaggeration in relation to culture from a linguistic standpoint entail investigating the relationship between language and society. People perceive and follow the social environment differently since they do not share the same ethnocultural community. Hyperbole can be single-word hyperbole, phrasal hyperbole, clausal

hyperbole, numerical hyperbole, hyperbole in superlative degree, comparison, and repetition. The use of hyperbole is entirely dependent on the user's preferences.

Literature review:

It has become the object of various studies by Uzbek linguists and foreign scientists. Some Uzbek linguists like Sh. A. Abdurahmonov, L.T. Bobohonova, A. Hozhiev, have worked on hyperbole by comparison with Russian and English scientists' work. However, it was used more effectively. It was called "mubolag'a" (exaggeration) and divided into three types: tablig', ig'roq and g'uluv. A. Hozhiev transliterated it as giperbola into Uzbek language and though it is a form of exaggeration of events, animals and situation: Qil ustida turibdi. Sariq chaqaga olmaydi. Sarhovuzdan katta edi kosasi [4]. Although there has been a significant amount of scientific research on the study of hyperbola as a stylistic tool using traditional structural-semantic and functional methods, there are a number of current issues with hyperbole, among which, on the one hand, this stylistic tool is considered one of the cognitive-stylistic categories; on the other hand, the linguo-cognitive basis of which has not yet been revealed, from the perspective of linguo-cognitive linguistics [5].

Based on the above considerations, it can be concluded that the basis of hyperbole, that is, its philosophical basis, is artistic (both prosaic and poetic) or simple, everyday exaggeration, although the meaning of exaggeration in modern linguistics and literature is reflected in encyclopedias and other scientific studies. An analysis of most scientific studies on hyperbole shows that most of the authors of these works classify hyperbola as "stylistic figures", sometimes they refer to hyperbole. Interpreted as a "trop", some consider it "a stylistic tool" some include it in the list of "figurative expressions", others describe it as "a means of influence" and so on [6].

Hyperbole is now attracting the attention of an increasing number of scholars as a distinct aspect of artistic and public speaking, as well as everyday speech of speakers/writers. It is also being studied extensively in linguistics, or rather, cognitive

stylistics, a relatively underdeveloped field of modern linguistics. It focuses on its linguo-cognitive, structural-semantic (static), communicative-pragmatic (dynamic), and linguo-culturological aspects, as well as its functional stylistic aspects.

Main part

Besides some researches on hyperbole, it was/is used in literature and conversation to describe qualities such as being extremely beautiful, graceful, brave, and so on. Since it is a common and universal tool to decorate speeches, it has been used by Uzbek writers. It is found mostly in fairy tales, legends, narratives and other genres of oral and written literature, romantic, humorous, satirical works. In Uzbek linguistics, “hyperbole” has been analysed within the frameworks of simile, metaphor, metonymy, and synecdoche. Similarities between an object and its intended meaning can be taken as the basis of hyperbole. Classic works on the art of hyperbole include “Tarjuman ul Baloga” by Umar Roduyoni, “Hadoyiq us sehr” by Rashididdin Vatvot, “Almo’jam” by Shams Qays Razi, and “Funun ul Balog’a” by Sheikh Ahmad Tarazi works that primarily emphasize the second type of hyperbole “**Ig’roq**”. Hyperbole was mostly employed it to highlight the protagonists of the work’s extreme beauty, strength, emotional status as well as their unmistakable superiority to others. The great Uzbek poet A. Navoiy, a representative of Uzbek literature and a master of figurative language, portrayed the hours of waiting a man would endure for his lady:

Kecha kelgumdur debon ul sarvi gulru kelmadi,
Ko’zlarimga kecha tong otquncha uyqu kelmadi.

(“Badoyi’ ul vasat”, gazel 608)

It is an exaggerated image of a man’s sleepless nights due to the non-arrival of his promised lady, but this situation can be imagined mentally and sometimes happens in real life.

Hyperbole is used in **lof** (it is a genre of Uzbek national folklore and means overstatement, exaggeration). The lof is one of the comic and humorous genres of the folklore of the Uzbek people. Particularly when Lof is presented in dialogical form,

participants try to use different figurative speech acts and create humour through the hyperbolic image with reference to an intended meaning. Lofchi (Lof-maker) is the kind of person who tells jokes and makes people laugh.

Original Version in the Uzbek language:

Bir lofchi ikkinchi lofchiga o'g'lini maqtadi:

- Mening o'g'lim ikki yosh bo'lishiga qaramay, bo'yi chunonam o'sib ketdiki, yulduzlarni qo'li bilan ushlab ko'rayabdi.

Ikkinchi lofchi dedi:

- O'g'lingiz yulduzlarni ushlayotganda boshiga biror narsa tegmadimi?

Birinchi lofchi bulutni aytayotgan bo'lsa kerk deb o'yladi va javob berdi:

- Ha.

Shunda ikkinchi lofchi dedi:

- Osha teggan narsa o'g'lim kiygan to'nning past qismi bo'ladi [8]

Some Uzbek linguists have focused on hyperbole, like Sh. A. Abdurahmonov and A. Hozhiev. They called hyperbole “mubolag'a” (exaggeration) and divided it into three groups: *tablig'*, *ig'roq* or *ifrot* and *g'uluv*. They are differentiated according to level of imagination.

Firstly, the exaggeration in the picture is acceptable to the mind, but it is not found in real life. This is called “**tablig'**” (meaning a strong one):

For instance: Olganing oltin, qidirganing kumush bo'lsin.

The second type is that this kind of hyperbolic description of the phenomenon is totally inconceivable. It is called **ig'roq** or **ifrot** (overstatement, exaggeration).

For instance: “Sar hovuzdan kata edi kossasi” (The bowl was bigger than the pool ...). (Alpomish – uzbek epic poem). The reader or listener could picture it, but they will not be able to comply with the logic, which explains something very enormous. TV programs might exaggerate it.

The third type is superior to the first two. It's called **g'uluv** (to make something loudly and excessively describe). That is why the hyperbole in this play is so far beyond the scope of human comprehension.

Such overstating examples can be found in the Uzbek folklore genre. For example: "G'orog'li qilichining har hamlasi – qirq ming lashkarning bo'ynini uzardi..." (Every attack of the Gorogli's sword stretched the neck of forty thousand soldiers). These examples are taken from the epic poems "Gorogli". However, hyperbole has been used for a long time and is still in use due to its intended meaning being conveyed rather than merely saying something.

Hyperbole in the Uzbek language can be represented by a single word (lexeme; these are phonemes, morphemes, and lexemes that represent the semantics of exaggeration), and stylistic figures include speech phrases, phrases with a specific structure, and syntactic devices, in short, larger than the word "hyperbole". For example, Sh. Mirzaxalilova has analysed 7 types of hyperbole that used in Uzbek languages with certain examples. She believed that hyperbola can be utilized as an event in modern English, Uzbek, as well as other languages through a system of invariant types of the following specific verbal tools-verbalizers [9]:

- 1) Fonomorfema (Phono-morpheme)
- 2) Morfema (Morpheme)
- 3) Leksema (Lexeme)
- 4) Frazema (word combinations or idioms)
- 5) Sintaksema (sentence)
- 6) Frazeoema (phraseological units)
- 7) Tekstema or disskursema (the whole text)

1. In phono-morpheme, certain vowels and consonants are pronounced as long as possible to differentiate the priority of the word.

In the English language: 1) vowels like: deeply, too, beautiful, hardly – [i:], [e], [u], [a:]: She breathed deeply then told him everything; 2) through consonants such as

devilishly, hellishly – [d], [h]: It was because a young boy was so hellishly hot that he did these very things;

In the Uzbek language: 1) vowels like: [u:], [o'], [e:], [ye:] in words such as sovuq, uzun, o'ta, eng, bag'oyat, benihoya, behad, behisob: Uning aytishicha, otasi bu ajoyib oila bilan benihoya mamnun emish; 2) through consonants such as [j], [r], [t] in the words juda, rosa, tor, [z] in word: zor, zo'r: Men o'rtoqlarimni ranjitishdan juda qo'rqaman.

2. In morpheme:

In English 1) adjective+est: He was the kindest person; I have ever met. 2) super, hyper, ultra+adjective: That was supersonic plane (daily plane);

In Uzbek: 1) base of the form be+ot: behad, benihoya, behimor, behisob – Sizdan behad minnatdorman. Katta rahmat [10]; 2) fe'l+mas (tolmas, o'lmas, charchamas, kelmas and others): Bu yo'l borsa kelmas.

3. In lexeme, the following types of parts of speech are used to make sentence more exaggerated in the English and Uzbek languages:

a) Adjectives:

In English: supreme, extreme, outstanding, everlasting, etc.

In Uzbek: oliy, ulug', yolg'iz, birgina, tovuqmiya, etc.

b) Pronouns:

In English: all, every, each, everybody, everything, everyone, nobody, no one, none, neither, etc.

In Uzbek: bor, bari, barisi, mavjud, hamma, har bir, har kim, har narsa, hech bir, hech narsa, hech bir kishi, etc.

c) Nouns:

In English: planet/on the planet, world.in the world, earth/in the earth, life/in one's life, etc.

In Uzbek: dunyoda, yer yuzida, jahonda, etc

d) Adverbs:

In English: always, never, ever, forever, for good, for years, for centuries, nowhere, everywhere, anywhere, etc.

In Uzbek: doimo, hech qachon, hech yerda, hayotda, har yerda, har joyda, har qayerda, qishin-yozin and etc: Momom bo'ychan, boshi kata, qoshlari siyrak, ko'zlari ko'm-ko'k, qo'llari, barmoqlari uzun-uzun, gap-so'zlari dadil, qishin-yozin ikki beti qip-qizil bo'lib yonib turadigan kampir edi.

e) Numbers:

In English: hundred(s), thousand(s), millions(s) ten(s), etc,

In Uzbek: yuz, ming, million, minglab, millionlab etc.

4. Word combinations or Idioms:

In English: on the earth/not on the earth, in the world/not in the world, for the world/not for the world, thousands of pardons, no one, nowhere but and etc.

In Uzbek: yer yuzida, yer kurrasida, hech bir inson, hech bir kimsa, hech bir jonzot, hech bir joyda, and etc.

5. On level of sentence:

In English: This man thought he had everything under control because he was rich [12].

In Uzbek: Aytishlariga qaraganda o'sha omadli Meshpolvon kelajakda o'z ishlari afsonaga aylanib, nomi tarixda qolishini hali bilmagan chog'laridayoq, tashqi qiyofasi bilan boshqalardan yaqqol ajralib turarkan: ikki lunji nog'ora, beti oftobdan zog'ora, jag'ida eshak tepkisi naqshlagan chandiq, qorni naq qirq pudlik sandiq, burni mushuknikidek puchuq, yelkasi baayni hurpaygan chum chuq, bo'yni oldinga enkaygan, quloqlari dinkaygan, oyoq bosishi ilang-bilang, boshi Yozyovon cho'ldek yap-yalang, ko'rinishidan kam gap-u anqov, aslida mahmadana-yu mijg'ov, ko'zlari boyqushnikidek ola... xullas, rosayam qiziq bola ekan.

6. Phraseological units:

In English: not for the world, for the world, swim or snack, cat-and-dog, to give the world to do something, hear a mile away and etc. For example: She can hear a pin drop a mile away.

In Uzbek: to'nini teskari kiymoq, boshi osmonga yetmoq, boshi yerga tekkuncha tazim qilmoq, kulini ko'kka sovrmoq, boshini olib ketmoq, joni halqumiga kelmoq, ikki oyog'ini qo'liga olib yugurmoq, yuragi yorilmoq, boshi qotmoq, otini boshqa qo'ymoq, ko'zi moshdek ochilmoq, almisoqdan qolgan, ikki gapning birida, ko'zi ko'r, qulog'i kar, yuragi shig' etib ketmoq. For example: G'ulomjonning yuragi shig' etib ketdi [15].

7. Hyperbole is made through the whole text:

In English: His hair, painfully red and cut close to his head, framed a milk-white, freckled face....

In Uzbek: Bir tavakkal buzadi ming qayg'uning qal'asin, Bir shirin so'z bitkazar, ming ko'ngilning yarasin.

After examining the lexical style device known as hyperbole and its Uzbek and Modern English equivalents, "mubolag'a" we came to the conclusion that their stylistic purpose is to convey feelings. Typically, the emotional meaning predominates over the logical one in hyperbole.

RESULTS

Following an examination of the scholars' work and materials available in Uzbek linguistics, the following conclusions were reached:

1. The study of language resources, such as the use of hyperbole in English and Uzbek, has had various origins, unique features, and objectives.
2. There are various types of hyperbole, including one-word, phrasal, clausal, numerical, superlative, comparative, and repetition hyperbole.
3. It can be made from parts of speech.
4. Hyperbole is frequently utilized to create humor, especially in the "Lof" genre.

5. There are three varieties in Uzbek: tablig', ig'roq or ifrot, and g'uluv. Their differences are based on their degree of imagination.
6. Sh. Mirzaxalilova lists seven verbalizers as techniques for incorporating hyperbole into speech.

DISCUSSION

This chapter covered how hyperbole is categorised and used in English and Uzbek, as well as how it differs from other literary devices and how it is comparable to them. It is well known that when someone wants to speak, he or she prefers to use metaphorical language. Hyperbole is the most well-liked and frequently employed stylistic device among the figurative devices. Exaggeration or hyperbole is used interchangeably to examine the definition of overacting thought.

Conclusion

The usage of hyperbole is a bit difficult to understand by different nation people due to bringing cultural related realia or legends into conversation. Because behind every single event or legends has own background that are common to people of a nation. Moreover, it is utilized on purpose like hide feelings toward someone or persuade. The use of hyperbole is entirely dependent on the user's preferences. Based on the considerations, it can be concluded that the basis of hyperbole, that is, its philosophical basis, is artistic (both prosaic and poetic) or simple, everyday exaggeration, although the meaning of exaggeration in modern linguistics and literature is reflected in encyclopedias and other scientific studies.

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